

ON COLLOIDAL ACIDS

An Attempt to find the Dissociation Constants of Gum Arabic and Polyacrylic Acids

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On the basis of the theory proposed by the author to account for the "Pallmann or solc oncentration effect" the following equation has been derived

$$p(H_c) = p(\theta K_s) + n \ln \alpha / (1 - \alpha)$$

in which (H_c) represents the H^+ ion activity of the sol of the colloidal acid, $\theta = C/(K_o + C)$, C being the concentration of the colloidal acid (unit arbitrary) K_o , a constant, K_s the surface dissociation constant and α , the degree of neutralisation of the acid.

The equation agrees well with the data on the neutralisation of gum arabic acid and polyacrylic acids investigated by Briggs and Samelson respectively. The pK_s of arabic acid and polyacrylic acids have been found to be 3.03 and 4.77 respectively. Conditions favourable for determining K_s directly have been discussed.

The electrochemical properties of gum arabic and polyacrylic acids have been investigated by several authors.¹⁻¹⁰ The results of such investigations show that at a given degree of neutralisation the p^H of the sol depends on the concentration of acid taken and also on the concentration of the added neutral salt. Different theories have been proposed to account for these facts. In the theory^{3,7} proposed earlier it has been assumed that the dissociation constants of the COOH groups present in a macromolecule differ from one another while in the theory proposed later^{6,8,9,10} all the COOH groups in a molecule are assumed to have the same dissociation constant, but it is modified by the electrostatic interaction of the other COOH groups already ionised. According to Overbeek⁸ if K_o be the dissociation constant of a COOH group, then the observed dissociation constant K is given by the expression

$$K = K_o \exp(-\Delta F/kT) \quad \dots \quad (a)$$

where ΔF represents the extra amount of free energy per COOH group required to cause further dissociation when the macromolecule has already acquired a charge say Z_e . Combining equation (a) with the Henderson equation, the following equation is obtained

$$p^H - pK_o - \log \alpha / (1 - \alpha) = \frac{0.434}{kT} \Delta F \quad (b)$$

Using random coil as a model, Hermans and Over-

beek¹¹ and others^{12,13} have deduced, for different forms of charge distribution, expressions for the electrical free energy F and hence for ΔF on the basis of the Debye-Huckel theory. It follows from equation (b) that ΔF can also be determined, for different values of α , by potentiometric titration when K_o is known. The theoretical expressions for ΔF combined with the possibility of its determination for different values of α have provided incentive for further research on this line. A detailed investigation, by potentiometric titration of polyglutamic acids^{14,15} and hydrolysed copolymers of maleic anhydride and alkyl vinyl ethers¹⁶ has been carried out with a view to ascertain helix-coil transition in them and the energy changes involved in such transition.

It may be pointed out that in equation (a) the effect of sol concentration on K has not been taken into consideration. In the present paper this effect on K will be considered on the basis of the theory recently proposed by the author. The main assumptions on which the theory is based are as follows :

(i) Each colloidal particle* is surrounded by an electrical double layer made up of two parts, (1) the fixed Stern¹⁷-Mukherjee¹⁸ layer and the diffuse (i.e. the Gouy-Chapman) layer.

(ii) The counter ions cannot go beyond the boundary of the diffuse double layer of the particle to which

* The colloidal particle may be a macro-molecule or a micelle.

they belong. When a particle moves sufficiently close to the reversible electrode placed in the sol so that the diffuse double layer is in contact with the electrode, then only the counter ions present in that part of the diffuse double layer can register their activity on the electrode.

(iii) Starting from the outermost boundary of the diffuse double layer, the number of counter ions per unit volume increases according to the Boltzmann distribution law as the surface of the particle is approached.

On the basis of the aforesaid assumptions it has been shown by the author in previous publications^{19,20} that if (H_c) represents the H^+ ion activity of a sol of a colloidal acid of concentration C (unit arbitrary) measured by the potentiometric method, θ the fraction of the surface per unit area of the electrode covered by the diffuse double layers of the particles and (H_i) the H^+ ion activity of the intermicellar liquid (i.e. the ultrafiltrate) then the following equation can be derived

$$(H_c) = (H_s)\theta + (H_i)(1 - \theta) \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

in which $\theta = C/(K_o + C)$, K_o a constant and (H_s) a proportionality constant which may be interpreted to represent the H^+ ion activity associated with a unit area of the diffuse double layer at the plane of contact with the reversible electrode.

For a well dialysed sol in which C is fairly large, (H_i) is very small compared to (H_c) or (H_s) and may be neglected. Equation (1) may then be written as

$$(H_c) = (H_s)\theta \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

*Let us now assume that (H_s) is proportional (if not equal) to $(H_a)^n$ and that for the exchange of H^+ ions between the fixed Stern-Mukherjee layer

* It may be pointed out that the H^+ ion activity (H_a) close to the COO^- groups attached to the surface of the macromolecule is much greater than (H_s) at the plane of contact of the diffuse double layer with the electrode. The Boltzmann distribution law is not likely to hold rigorously so close to the surface as the charges are concentrated on points (i.e. COO^- groups) and not smeared. Furthermore, the surface potential ψ_o will be much greater than kT/e and hence the Debye-Huckel approximation will not be valid. On the other hand in the equation $(H_s) = K'(H_a)^n$ any given value of (H_a) can be equated to any given value of (H_s) by properly choosing n and K' .

and the diffuse double layer, the following equation holds good ;

$$(H_a)(\alpha) = K_a(1 - \alpha) \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

where K_a is the dissociation constant, α , the degree of ionisation i.e. the bare fraction and $(1 - \alpha)$, the fraction covered by the bound H^+ ions per unit area of the Stern-Mukherjee layer and n a constant.

It then follows from equation (3) that

$$(H_a)^n = (K_a)^n (1 - \alpha)^n / (\alpha)^n \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

Since it has been assumed that $(H_s) = K'(H_a)^n$ it follows from the equations (2) and (4) that

$$(H_c) = \theta K'(K_a)^n (1 - \alpha)^n / (\alpha)^n = \theta K_s (1 - \alpha)^n / (\alpha)^n \quad (5)$$

where $K_s = K'(K_a)^n$ and may be termed the surface dissociation constant of the acid. Equation (5) may also be written as follows ;

$$P^{(H_c)} = P^{(\theta K_s)} + n \log \alpha / (1 - \alpha) \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

Verification of equation (6)

At constant volume, Briggs⁴ has determined, by the potentiometric method, the H^+ ion activity of gum arabic acid sols during their neutralisation by NaOH. According to Briggs 1 gram of arabic acid requires for its neutralisation 85×10^{-5} gram equivalents of NaOH. Some of the data of Briggs⁴ taken from table 3 of his paper are recorded in the tables 1 and 2 in which the concentration C of arabic acid has been expressed in gram per 1000 grams of water.

Samelson¹⁰ has carried out an extensive investigation on the neutralisation of polyacrylic acids (PAA) under a variety of conditions. Some of his data are recorded in the tables 3 and 4 in which the concentration C has been expressed in terms of "grundmolarity" i.e. 72 grams of the acid in 1000 ml of water. In this paper the term normality will be used instead of "Grundmolarity."

It may be mentioned that the systems to which the data recorded in the tables 1 to 6 refer contained no neutral salt.

For a given concentration of an acid (θK_s) and n have been found by plotting $P^{(H_c)}$ against $\log \alpha / (1 - \alpha)$. The intercept on the ordinate corresponding

to $\alpha=0.5$ gives $P^{(\theta K_s)}$ and the slope of the straight line gives n .

For the dilute sol of gum arabic acid containing 0.625 gram of the acid per 1000 grams of water the values of $\log \alpha/(1-\alpha)$ from +0.038 and above it have been used for the following reason. In this case (H_c) is quite small compared to (H_s), since $H_s=(H_c)/\theta$ and θ is very small as the amount of acid used is only 0.625 gram per 1000 grams of water. In the calculation of α , the contribution of (H_c) has been taken into account by Briggs and not that of (H_s), but this can be done without introducing appreciable error only when NaOH added is sufficiently large to make (H_s) negligible compared to (Na^+). For the dilute solution of the acid this condition is satisfied when about 50 per cent of the acid taken has been neutralised by NaOH. -

TABLE 1. GUM ARABIC ACID

$P^{(\theta K_s)}=3.30$		$n=1.21$		
C	$(\alpha)/(1-\alpha)$	$\log (\alpha)/(1-\alpha)$	Values of $P^{(H_c)}$	
			Observed	Calculated from equation (6)
50	0.200	-0.699	2.45	2.45
„	0.401	-0.397	2.81	2.82
„	0.555	-0.256	3.00	2.99
„	0.755	-0.116	3.15	3.15
„	1.045	+0.019	3.34	3.32
„	2.042	+0.310	3.68	3.68
„	3.048	+0.484	3.90	3.89
„	5.055	+0.704	4.13	4.15
„	11.070	+1.045	4.60	4.57

TABLE 2. GUM ARABIC ACID

$P^{(\theta K_s)}=4.88$		$n=1.60$		
C	$(\alpha)/(1-\alpha)$	$\log (\alpha)/(1-\alpha)$	Values of $P^{(H_c)}$	
			Observed	Calculated from eq ⁿ (6)
0.625	1.091	+0.038	4.95	4.95
„	2.070	+0.316	5.39	5.39
„	5.110	+0.708	6.01	6.01

TABLE 3. POLYACRYLIC ACID (PAA)

$P^{(\theta K_s)}=5.98$		$n=2.00$		
Normality of PAA	(α)	$\log (\alpha)/(1-\alpha)$	Values of $P^{(H_c)}$	
			Observed	Calculated from eq ⁿ (6)
0.0704	0.251	-0.475	4.95	5.03
„	0.350	-0.269	5.50	5.44
„	0.652	+0.273	6.53	6.53
„	0.800	+0.602	7.11	7.18

TABLE 4. POLYACRYLIC ACID

$P^{(\theta K_s)}=6.08$		$n=1.94$		
Normality of PAA	(α)	$\log (\alpha)/(1-\alpha)$	Values of $P^{(H_c)}$	
			Observed	Calculated from eq ⁿ (6)
0.0527	0.251	-0.475	5.04	5.16
„	0.350	-0.269	5.59	5.58
„	0.652	+0.273	6.62	6.61
„	0.800	+0.602	7.23	7.25

It will be noticed from data recorded in the tables 1 and 2 that for the arabic acid sols, the agreement between the observed and calculated values of $P^{(H_c)}$ is quite good. For the concentrated sol α varies from 17 to about 91 per cent and within this range (θK_s) remains constant. For each of the polyacrylic acid sols also (tables 3 and 4) the agreement between the observed and calculated values of $P^{(H_c)}$ may be considered fair when α varies from 0.25 to 0.80.

The values of $P^{(\theta K_s)}$ for the concentrated and the dilute sols of arabic acid are 3.30 and 4.88 respectively, while those for the 0.0704 N and 0.0527 N polyacrylic acid sols are 5.98 and 6.08 respectively.

Determination of the constant K_s

(a) *Arabic acid.*

For finding the surface dissociation constant K_s , it is necessary to know θ and therefore, K_o in the

expression for θ . In a previous paper,²¹ for the calculation of osmotic pressure of arabic acid sols measured by Brigg's, the value of K_o in the expression for θ has been found to be 43.3. The same value of K_o may be used here also. The pH of an arabic acid sol during neutralisation with NaOH has also been determined by Mukherjee and Ghosh.²² Their data marked with an asterisk along with those of Briggs are recorded in table 5.

TABLE 5. ARABIC ACID

$K_o(\text{in } \theta) = 43.3$					
C	θ	$\alpha/(1-\alpha)$	$P^{(\theta K_s)}$	$P^{(\theta)}$	P^{K_s}
50	0.536	1	3.30	0.27	3.03
0.625	0.0142	1	4.88	1.85	3.03
*9.8	0.186	1	3.75	0.73	3.02

It will be noticed from the data recorded in table 5 that P^{K_s} for gum arabic acid is 3.03. It may be concluded from an analysis of the data recorded in the tables 1, 2, and 5 that in the case of gum arabic acid K_s remains constant when the degree of neutralisation varies from 17 to about 91 per cent and the concentration varies from 50 to 0.625 grams per 1000 grams of water.

(b) *Polyacrylic acid.*

In a previous publication²³ attempt was made to find the K_s of PAA by adopting the same procedure as discussed above. Only three data were then available and so it was not possible to find θ and K_s accurately. Since then a photostat copy of Samelson's thesis has been received and it is found to contain sufficient data for an accurate estimation of θ and hence K_s .

In table 6 are recorded some of the data of Samelson¹⁰ along with one of Kern⁵ marked with an asterisk. When no neutral salt has been added to a sol of PAA at a given degree of neutralisation then it follows from equation (2) that

$$\frac{1}{(H_c)} = \frac{K_o}{(H_s)} \cdot \frac{1}{C} + \frac{1}{(H_s)} \quad \dots (7)$$

Hence $\frac{1}{(H_c)}$ has been plotted against $\frac{1}{C}$ and from the slope and intercept of the straight line K_o has been found to be 1.05.

TABLE 6.

$K_o(\text{in } \theta) = 1.05$						
Nor- mality	$(H_c) \times 10^7$	$\alpha/(1-\alpha)$	$P^{(\theta K_s)}$	θ	$P^{(\theta)}$	P^{K_s}
*0.125	17.4	1	5.76	0.1064	0.97	4.79
0.0704	10.5	1	5.98	0.0628	1.20	4.78
0.0527	8.32	1	6.08	0.0478	1.32	4.76
0.0348	4.68	1	6.33	0.0321	1.49	4.84
0.0263	5.01	1	6.30	0.0244	1.61	4.69
0.0197	3.02	1	6.52	0.0184	1.74	4.78
0.0174	2.51	1	6.60	0.0163	1.79	4.81
						Average 4.78

It will be noticed from the data recorded in table 6 that the average value of P^{K_s} is 4.78. Therefore, it may be concluded from the data recorded in the tables 3, 4 and 6 that within the limits of experimental error P^{K_s} of polyacrylic acid remains constant when its grumdolarity (i.e. Normality) varies from 0.125 to 0.0174 and the degree of neutralisation α , varies from 0.25 to 0.80.

Elimination of 'Pallmann effect' by adding neutral salt.

The particles (macromolecules) of a PAA sol are negatively charged with H^+ as counter ions in the diffuse double layer. At constant volume, when a neutral salt $M^+ A^-$ is added to such a sol, the cations M^+ enter the diffuse double layers of the particles and release H^+ ions which pass into the intermicellar liquid and increase (H_i) . The equilibrium between the bound H^+ ions in the Stern-Mukherjee layer and those in the diffuse layer is disturbed. Consequently a few COOH groups in the Stern-Mukherjee layer dissociate and the H^+ ions thus released enter the diffuse double layer to restore equilibrium. Therefore, the net effect of addition of $M^+ A^-$ is that some H^+ ions are transferred from the Stern-Mukherjee layer and the diffuse double layer to the intermicellar liquid. As the concentration of $M^+ A^-$ in the PAA sol is increased (H_i) increases and the difference between (H_c) and (H_i) decreases. Therefore, it is possible theoretically at least, that at a sufficiently high concentration of $M^+ A^-$, (H_i) becomes equal to (H_c) . Under this condition, it follows from equation (1) that ;

$$(H_c) - (H_i) = O = [(H_s) - (H_i)]\theta \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

Since θ is not zero, therefore, under this condition

$$(H_c) = (H_i) = (H_s)$$

If the PAA sol used has already been neutralised to the extent of 50 per cent (i.e. $\alpha=0.5$), then under the aforesaid conditions, we can write

$$(H_c) = (H_i) = (H_s) = K_s \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

The question may be raised that since, α , the degree of neutralisation of the PAA sol has already been adjusted to 0.5 any further increase in α caused by the addition of $M^+ A^-$ will make the ratio $\alpha/(1-\alpha)$ greater than unity for which correction is to be introduced into equation (9). The following consideration will show that such a correction will be negligible even when the concentration of a PAA sol is as low as 0.0348 N. In this case, the concentration of the unneutralised acid is 0.0174 N, since $\alpha=0.5$ and a further increase in its dissociation by 0.1 per cent will raise the value of (H_i) to 1.74×10^{-5} N which is slightly higher than the extrapolated value of (H_i) found at an infinite concentration of $M^+ A^-$. Obviously a 0.1 per cent increase in α can be considered negligible.

Samelson's¹⁰ data on the effect of addition of NaCl to a 0.0348 N PAA sol already neutralised to $\alpha=0.5$ are recorded in table 7 in which M represents

TABLE 7
Con. of PAA=0.0348 N

$\alpha/(1-\alpha)$	$(H_c) \times 10^6$	$1/(H_c) \times 10^{-5}$	M	1/M	Extrapolated Values for 1/M=0	
					$1/(H_c)$	P^{K_s}
1	10.23	0.98	0.414	2.41	—	—
1	7.08	1.41	0.207	4.83	5.85×10^4	4.77
1	4.68	2.14	0.104	9.60		
1	2.63	3.80	0.0518	19.30		

the molar concentration of NaCl. Fig. 1 represents a plot of $\frac{1}{(H_c)}$ against $\frac{1}{(M)}$.

The extrapolated value of $1/(H_c)$ and hence that of $1/K_s$ is 5.85×10^4 when $1/M=0$. Therefore, $K_s=1.71 \times 10^{-5}$ or $P^{K_s}=4.77$.

Since the value of P^{K_s} found by using equation (6) is 4.78 and that found by extrapolation corresponding to $1/M=0$ is 4.77 so the agreement between them may be considered quite satisfactory. Hence K_s is a constant within the range of α mentioned already (viz. 0.25 to 0.8).

It may also be pointed out that under the conditions of Donnan membrane equilibrium when the concentration of NaCl added to a PAA sol is very high the Donnan E.M.F. between the sol and the outside solution vanishes.

In conclusion it may be stated that what has been found is K_s the surface dissociation constant and an equation connecting K_s to K_a , the dissociation constant of the COOH i.e. the acidic group. Assuming K' equal to unity K_a can be found.

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